

Central Bohemian Region Pilot

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Specifics of the Central Bohemian Region

- Biggest and highest populated region in the Czech Republic (1,4 mil. of inhabitants from 10 mil. in total)
- Highest number of municipalities with their own authority (1140 from 6250 in total)
- Highest number of small villages under 500 inhabitants
- Intraregional disparity (rural vs. metropolitan areas, capital in the middle of the region)

Challenges of the Central Bohemian Region

- Sustain of the unique settlement structure (and following infrastructure)
- Support wellbeing and sustainable development (incl. biodiversity)
- Deal with digital transition and goals of climate neutrality
- COVID-19 recovery
- Strengthen of resilience (incl. energy crisis)

SMART Concept and supporting of innovations as main tools

On the national level:

- Strategic document „SMART Cities Concept - resilience through SMART Solutions for municipalities, cities and regions“ (approved by the government in May 2022; co-authors)
- SMART Solutions definition (incl. soft innovative tools; fundamental tools of (regional) sustainable development)
- Holistic/multidisciplinary approach based on quadrupel helix collaboration with stakeholders/multi-stakeholders collaboration
- National „Implementation Plan“ (approved by the government in May 2022; co-authors)

SMART Concept (Czech Republic)

Source: SMART Cities Concept - resilience through SMART Solutions for municipalities, cities and regions

Other (key) development documents to work with

On the regional level (authority):

- Development Strategy of the Central Bohemian Region for 2019 - 2024, up to 2030 (not updated from 2019)
- Action Plan (not prepared yet)

On the regional level (LAGs):

- Strategic document (vast majority of them incorporated SMART Concept principles)

Main barriers

- Specifics of the Central Bohemian Region (both opportunity and barriers)
- COVID-19 restrictions (opportunities for collaboration)
- Low level of understanding of the SMART Concept (holistic "modern" approach; technology vs. community)
- Low level of using of strategic documents (as a road map) on the regional level (Regional Authority)
- No regional partners (powerful policy-makers, situation changed after elections; no long-term vision)
- Unclear funding (both national and EU level)

Action Plan

Main purpose:

- Building of the stronger, resilient and sustainable region (both rural and also metropolitan areas)
- Wellbeing (minimizing of intraregional disparities; incl. (de)population)
- Support of multi-stakeholder collaboration (from QH to penta/quintuple helix = both sustainable/environmentally “friendly” and social dimensions)

Through implementation of the SMART Concept

From QH to penta/quintuple helix

Source: Knowledge Society Handbook, 2016

PoliRural technical tools

Active using:

- Rural Attractiveness Explorer (Czech Rural Attractiveness, Czech language)
- Digital Innovation Hub (webinars)
- Atlas of Best Practices

Semantic tools are not suitable, Czech language is too complicated...

PoliRural methodology tools (guides)

Active using of all materials is planned (sharing with all relevant stakeholders, no translation is planned).

- Guide to Deep Dives (Covid)
- Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform)
- Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal)
- The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change
- D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology

Thank you for your attention.

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